

Before, During and After BM-5102

Ryan and Deci (2000) define intrinsic motivation as the pursuit of personal pleasure or contentment when doing an activity. They also define extrinsic motivation as an activity that is done for another separate, distinct, outcome. Therefore, my main goal for pursuing my Master was extrinsic, in the sense that I want to make my parents proud. All my other siblings have achieved graduate degrees in their own respective fields, so my parents thought that a graduate degree of my own was called for. I did not want to do a Master in my previous field, as I wanted to learn something new. So, I saw Master of management as an opportunity to expand my skill set even further. I have also experienced working with excellent managers who can make holistic and inclusive plans, and take care of their worker's well-being. Despite this, I have also worked with managers who were lacking in this aspect. Therefore, I found that the prospect of learning the conducts of being a better manager could be seen as another motivation. I wanted to develop myself into becoming a competent manager and employee, with the relevant knowledge to help bring success to any organisation that I would potentially work for. Although these motivations are contrasting in nature, as one is intrinsic, while the other is extrinsic, they both hold great importance.

I joined Master of Management with my friends, some of which were from my degree days, some were not. The field was new to me, as I had a geography and development background, but I was willing to learn and be competent at it. The first task under the organisational behaviour module was to write a review of a global company of our choosing, looking at how they implement personalities, individual differences and mental ability in their hiring process and management of their employees. I chose to write about Nike as a global brand, the most valuable sports brand in branded footwear with an industry-leading 38% shares (Ozanian, 2019). Their position in the industry was a point of interest for me, as well as their stance in promoting diversity. We submitted our papers to Microsoft Teams and our opinions were asked during the next tutorial class. I was asked which company I chose, and we discussed it. I feel this form of peer-to-peer learning was effective, as it allowed us to engage with our peers and discuss points which may or may not be apparent to said peers. Nonoka, as cited in Noriko (2009), stated that this new form of knowledge relies on inert understandings, subjective intuitions relying on instincts, to create an environment that is complimented by these various viewpoints. As the current situation facilitates a shift towards online modes of learning, I thought the application of peer-to-peer learning was questionable at first. The session was executed adequately, even though discussion amongst peers was relatively minimal. Despite this, it was an interesting start and there was still room for improvement.

When it was time to form groups, I would naturally group up with my friends. But, for the Organisational Behaviour module, we were split up into different tutorial groups and I was grouped separately from my friends. The group work was given during said tutorial groups, so we thought that grouping could only be done within said groups. But, this was not the case. As down the line we found out that we could form groups

irregardless of the tutorial groups. For the Group work assignment, We were told to pick a topic out of the 26 that were proposed by our lecturer. I formed a group with another friend who was in the same tutorial group, and a random peer. We chose the topic *“Explore diversity management strategies for attracting, selecting, developing, and retaining diverse employees: A Case of BSP Brunei”*. We would look into each component of the diversity management strategy of Brunei Shell Petroleum, putting emphasis on the stages of attracting, selecting, developing and retaining their diverse workforce. We wanted to interview As we were juggling multiple assignments given close together, less emphasis was put on the group work assignment. My group and I would still meet, but it was not as much as I would have liked. Eventually, I learned that my group members had to resign from the master in management programme due to varying opportunities that presented themselves. One member got offered to study abroad, while the other was offered a job. This left me alone to do the work. After consulting with the lecturer and my other friends, my other friends and I decided to merge me into their group of 3, as one of their members also left due to personal reasons, and their selected topic required 4 people. My new group and I worked on the topic *“Airline strategies amidst Covid-19 and its impact on team performance. This case study draws on a mixed method study of Brunei airline pilots in order to examine the impact of Covid-19 on pilots' trust, morale, and organizational commitment. Interview at least 22 pilots”*. This new topic looks at the strategies of Royal Brunei, the flag bearer airline company in Brunei Darussalam, in responding to the COVID-19 pandemic. As we wanted to see the impact it had on pilots, we prepared interview questions, as well as survey questionnaires pertaining to the themes of trust, morale and organisational commitment. We reached out to the pilots while stating our research. They answered the surveys, while we set up two focus groups to gather primary data. One group consisted of captains and senior first officers, while the other group comprised of first officers. We analysed our findings, comparing it to the strategies employed by other countries, and discussed the findings with regards to the three main themes of the study.

The second major assignment that we had to do was the individual analysis assignment. This assignment was more demanding in the sense that our lecturer required us to submit weekly updates. It started with a Individual analysis form, then came the final version of the IA form, then the IA proposal plan skeleton, and others. I was supposed to do research on the relationship between belongingness and motivation to do well for people from ethnic minority groups in Brunei. It would have been a qualitative type of study, where I would interview people from ethnic minority groups. But, the required ethics form to approach companies and conduct interviews could not be processed by the assistant registrar. Therefore, I was not able to do the research that I originally planned. The lecturer stated that this change of events was due to internal conflict, as the SBE department decided that undergraduate and postgraduate students who were not doing research could not collect primary data as it could be a conflict of interest for those who actually took specific research courses. She detailed that a topic that she gave was similar with another topic a lecturer was about to research on. This would make UBD look unethical if both parties were to approach the

same stakeholders. My lecturer was unsure what to do, but eventually she decided for us to write a systematic literature review.

We were tasked to complete the systematic literature review in just two weeks, on top of the other assignments, tests, and presentations that were assigned from the start of the semester. Due to this, I feel like the quality of my IA would be higher if given adequate time. Also, we only learned aspects of organisational behaviour in the beginning, but not throughout the duration of the module. As the module progressed, we would learn less about organisational behaviour and more about research methods. Tutorial classes were catered towards question and answer sessions for our assignments. Despite this, the content that my lecturer uploaded on teams would prove valuable as it gives insight on organisational behaviour.

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